

Studies on Thiazolidinones. Part XI* : Synthesis and Fungitoxicities of Thiazolidinones, Thiohydantoin and Their Derivatives Derived from Thiosemicarbazones

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Several thiazolidinones, thiohydantoin and their arylidene derivatives, dibromides of the arylidene derivatives and sulphonamido phenylazo compounds have been prepared from the thiosemicarbazones obtained from aldehydes and ketones with thiosemicarbazide. The structures of the compounds have been confirmed from spectral and analytical data. The antibacterial and antifungal activities of these compounds have been evaluated.

IN continuation of our earlier work on thiazolidinone and thiohydantoin^{1,2} derivatives, the present study deals with the synthesis of some thiazolidinone and thiohydantoin derivatives with a view to evaluating their antibacterial and antifungal activities. Although several aromatic aldehydethiosemicarbazones have been used to prepare thiazolidinones³, heterocyclic systems have not been explored. Therefore, in the present study a few thiazolidinones (II), thiohydantoin (III) and several of their derivatives (IV-IX) have been synthesised from heterocyclic thiosemicarbazones (Scheme 1) according to the procedure described in our earlier communication⁴.

A modified procedure⁴ was utilised to isolate the dibromo derivatives (VI and VII), where the bromination was conducted in chloroform medium and kept overnight. After removing the solvent the residue was extracted with aqueous H₂SO₄ and basified with ammonia to get the desired compounds. The ¹H nmr spectrum of thiazolidinone (II; R₁=C₆H₅-, R₂=H) derived from benzaldehydethiosemicarbazone and monochloroacetic acid gave two singlets at δ 4.15 and 6.10 corresponding to methylene and methin protons. The benzylidene derivative (IV; R₁=R₂=C₆H₅-, R₃=H) gave two singlets at δ 6.15 and δ 6.37 for the two methin groups. The downfield singlet at δ 6.37 corresponds to the exocyclic methin proton as it experiences the deshielding effect of carbonyl and the upfield singlet at δ 6.15 corresponds to the methin proton adjacent to the azine group. In the ir spectrum, the carbonyl absorption of the thiazolidinone (II) appeared at 1750 cm⁻¹ whereas in the benzylidene derivative (IV) it showed at 1730 cm⁻¹. The bathochromic shift is due to the conjugation of the carbonyl group with the exocyclic carbon-carbon double bond.

1. NaOAc, EtOH; 2. Cl.CH₂.COOH, NaOAc, EtOH;
3. Cl.OH₂.COOH, Pyridine; 4. RCHO, HOAc, NaOAc;
5. Br₂.CHCl₃; 6. NaNO₂, HCl, H₂N.C₆H₄.SO₂NH₂.

Scheme 1

Fungicidal and bactericidal activities :

The fungicidal activities of several representative compounds were evaluated against *T. mentagrophytes*

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and *A. niger* as the test fungi on Sabouraud's broth medium. 3-(Thienylidene-2-amino)-5-sulphonamidophenyldiazo-2-thiohydantion (IX; $R_1 = C_6H_5S$, $R_2 = H$) was found to be most active against *A. niger* in a concentration of 25 $\mu\text{g/ml}$. Bactericidal potency against *E. coli*, *S. typhi*, *S. aureus* were not encouraging with the thiazolidinone compounds.

Experimental

All melting points are uncorrected. Ir spectra of the compounds were recorded on KBr disc in Perkin-Elmer 521 spectrophotometer. Nmr spectra of the compounds were recorded in CDCl_3 solution with $(\text{CH}_3)_4\text{Si}$ as internal standard ($\delta = 0$ ppm) and recorded on Varian HA-60 spectrometer.

Benzaldehydethiosemicarbazone (I; $R_1 = C_6H_5$, $R_2 = H$):

Thiosemicarbazide (9.1 gm) in hot water (50 ml), and glacial acetic acid (2 ml) was added to a solution of freshly distilled benzaldehyde (10.6 gm) in ethanol (15 ml). The solution was refluxed with stirring for one hour and cooled during which the thiosemicarbazone separated out. It was purified by dissolving in warm 10% HCl using norite and reprecipitated by adding NaHCO_3 , m.p. 154° ; yield-88% (Found: S, 17.91, $C_8H_9N_3S$ requires S, 17.88).

2-(Benzylideneazine-2)-4-thiazolidinone (II; $R_1 = C_6H_5$, $R_2 = H$): A mixture of benzaldehydethiosemicarbazone (1.79 gm), monochloroacetic acid (1.3 gm), anhyd. NaOAc (1 gm) in ethanol (25 ml) was heated under reflux for five hours on a water bath with occasional shaking. Ethanol was distilled off and the reaction mixture was poured into water. The white solid obtained was filtered, washed with hot water and recrystallised from glacial acetic acid; m.p. 252° ; yield-80% (Found: S, 14.43, $C_{10}H_9N_3SO$ requires S, 14.61%); $\lambda_{\text{max}}^{\text{KBr}}$ (cm^{-1}): 3410 ($-\text{NH}-$), 2905 ($-\text{CH}-$ deformation in $-\text{CH}_2-$), 1750 ($\text{C}=\text{O}$); NMR(CDCl_3) δ : 4.15 (s, $-\text{CH}_2-$, 2H), 6.10 (s, $-\text{CH}=\text{}$, 1H), 7.30 (m, aromatic protons, 5H); Mol. Wt. Calcd. 209 observed M/e (MS) 209 (M^+).

5-Benzal-2-(benzylideneazine-2)-4-thiazolidinone (IV; $R_1 = R_2 = C_6H_5$, $R_3 = H$): A mixture of azine-4-thiazolidinone (0.22 gm), benzaldehyde (0.2 gm) and anhyd. NaOAc (0.5 gm) in glacial acetic acid (10 ml) was refluxed for two hours. After cooling it was poured into crushed ice. The yellow mass obtained was filtered, washed several times with water and recrystallised from acetic acid, m.p. 246° ; yield -80% (Found: S, 10.18, $C_{17}H_{13}N_3SO$ requires S, 10.32%); $\lambda_{\text{max}}^{\text{KBr}}$ (cm^{-1}): 3400 ($-\text{NH}-$ broad), 1730 ($\text{C}=\text{O}$), 1530 ($\text{CN}-$ stretching); NMR (CDCl_3) δ : 6.15 (s, $-\text{CH}=\text{}$, 1H), 6.37 (s, $-\text{exomethylene CH}$, 1H), 7.40 (m, aromatic protons, 10H); Mol. Wt. Calcd. 307 observed (MS) M/e 307 (M^+).

Bromination of IV ($R_1 = R_2 = C_6H_5$, $R_3 = H$):

A solution of the benzylidene derivative (IV) (0.01M) in chloroform was treated with bromine in chloroform and left overnight. Solvent was removed and the residue was extracted with aqueous H_2SO_4 when the solution gave deep yellow dibromide after basification with ammonia, m.p. 250° ; yield-65% (Found: Br, 34.23, $C_{17}H_{13}N_3SO\text{Br}_2$ requires Br, 34.26%).

3-Benzylideneamino-2-thiohydantoin (III; $R_1 = C_6H_5$, $R_2 = H$): A mixture of benzaldehydethiosemicarbazone (1.8 gm) and monochloroacetic acid (0.94 gm) was treated with dry pyridine (15 ml) and warmed a little till an exothermic reaction took place. After cooling, the reaction mixture was treated with ethanol (10 ml) and refluxed for two hours. The contents were poured into crushed ice when a grey compound separated out; filtered, dried and recrystallised from ethanol as colourless solid, m.p. $>250^\circ$; yield-75% (Found: S, 14.50, $C_{10}H_9N_3OS$ requires S, 14.61%).

3-(Benzylideneamino)-5-sulphonamido-phenylazo-2-thiohydantoin (IX; $R_1 = C_6H_5$, $R_2 = H$):

Sulphanilamide (0.45 gm) dissolved in glacial acetic acid (1 ml) and water (25 ml) was diazotised with NaNO_2 (0.25 gm in 30 ml of water) in an ice bath. The resulting diazo solution was added gradually with stirring to a previously cooled solution of thiohydantoin (0.4 gm) in NaOH (0.5 gm in

TABLE I

R_1	R_2	Thiosemicarbazone(I)		Thiazolidinone(II)		Thiohydantoin(III)				
		m.p.	% Sulphur		m.p.	% Sulphur		m.p.	% Sulphur	
			Found	Calcd.		Found	Calcd.		Found	Calcd.
p-Anisyl	H	170	15.17	15.31	245	12.56	12.85	240	12.71	12.85
Pyridyl-2	H	154	17.50	17.78	251	14.32	14.54	239	14.42	14.54
Thienyl-2	H	186	34.44	34.59	235	28.26	28.44	220	28.39	28.44
Furyl-2	H	154	18.78	18.93	210	15.16	15.31	220	15.40	15.31
Methyl	Methyl	179	24.21	24.43	168	18.67	18.71	266	18.65	18.71
Methyl	Thienyl-2	149	32.09	32.16	182	26.63	26.78	216	26.42	26.68
Methyl	Furyl-2	144	18.85	18.93	153	14.19	14.35	244	14.25	14.35
p-Chlorophenyl	H	203	14.78	14.99	246	12.60	12.62	255	12.46	12.62

TABLE 2

Nature of R ₁	Nature of R ₂	Nature of R ₃	Arylidene thiazolidinone(IV)			Dibromides(VI)		
			m.p.	% Sulphur Found	% Sulphur Calcd.	m.p.	% Bromine Found	% Bromine Calcd.
Phenyl	H	p-Chlorophenyl	> 250	9.28	9.37	> 250	31.82	31.91
p-Chlorophenyl	H	Phenyl	> 260	9.16	9.37	> 250	31.75	31.91
p-Chlorophenyl	H	p-Chlorophenyl	> 260	8.80	8.51	> 250	29.63	29.86
p-Anisyl	H	Phenyl	247	9.28	9.49	239(d)	31.92	32.19
p-Anisyl	H	p-Chlorophenyl	268	8.57	8.61	250(d)	30.25	30.10
Pyridyl-2	H	Phenyl	252	10.08	10.39	> 250	34.36	34.19
Pyridyl-2	H	p-Chlorophenyl	> 260	9.27	9.34	> 250	—	—
Thienyl-2	H	Phenyl	229	20.38	20.45	257	33.73	33.83
Furyl-2	H	Phenyl	> 260	10.63	10.77	> 250	35.00	35.01
Thienyl-2	H	p-Chlorophenyl	235	18.26	18.42	260	—	—
Furyl-2	H	p-Chlorophenyl	250	9.32	9.65	217	32.41	32.56
Methyl	Methyl	Phenyl	248	12.17	12.35	246	38.12	38.19
-do-	-do-	p-Chlorophenyl	> 260	10.79	10.90	> 250	35.06	35.28
-do-	Thienyl-2	Phenyl	247	19.43	19.57	> 250	32.55	32.86
-do-	Furyl-2	-do-	231	10.40	10.29	> 250	33.69	33.97

TABLE 3

R ₁	R ₂	Arylidene thiohydantoin(V)			Dibromide(VII)			Sulphonamido derivative(IX)		
		m.p.	% Sulphur		m.p.	% Bromine		m.p.	% Nitrogen	
			Found	Calcd.		Found	Calcd.		Found	Calcd.
Phenyl	H	248	10.31	10.42	> 250	—	—	—	—	—
p-Chlorophenyl	H	> 260	9.30	9.37	> 250	—	—	232	19.03	19.24
p-Anisyl	H	220	9.37	9.49	> 250	31.92	32.19	196	10.25	10.48
Pyridyl-2	H	189	10.07	10.39	> 250	34.31	34.19	250	20.20	24.32
Thienyl-2	H	201	20.36	20.45	246	33.90	33.83	247	20.41	20.59
Furyl-2	H	245	10.54	10.77	> 265	35.00	35.01	224	21.26	21.43
Methyl	Methyl	218	12.12	12.35	> 250	38.06	38.19	250	23.60	23.73
Methyl	Thienyl-2	226	19.33	19.57	> 250	32.55	32.86	250	19.82	19.91
Methyl	Furyl-2	192	10.17	10.29	> 250	33.69	33.97	250	20.65	20.69

TABLE 4—SULPHONAMIDO DERIVATIVES OF THIAZOLIDINONE(VIII)

R ₁	R ₂	m.p.	Colour	% Nitrogen	
				Found	Calcd.
Phenyl	H	230	Yellow	20.67	20.90
p-Anisyl	H	235	Yellow	19.32	19.44
Thienyl-2	H	205	Brown	20.39	20.50
Furyl-2	H	207(d)	Red	22.26	22.36
Furyl-2	Methyl	166	Red	20.46	20.69
Thienyl-2	Methyl	185	Orange	19.98	19.91

20 ml of water) kept in an ice bath. After addition, the mixture was stirred mechanically for half an hour during which the yellow coloured azo dye separated out. It was filtered and recrystallised from ethanol, m.p. 267° yield—48% (Found : N, 21.42, C₁₆H₁₈N₂SO requires N, 21.67%).

The physical and analytical data of other thiosemicarbazones, thiazolidinones and thiohydantoin; arylidene thiazolidinones and their dibromides,

arylidene and sulphonamido compounds of thiohydantoin and sulphonamido derivatives of thiazolidinones prepared by following the above general procedures have been presented in Tables 1, 2, 3 and 4 respectively.

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